

FACTORS THAT DETERMINE THE MENTAL HEALTH OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12594109>

Abstract. *This article examines the factors that influence and determine the mental health of future teachers. It is proved that the methodological and methodological foundations of research work have been developed.*

Keywords: *teacher, health, profession, factor, mental stress, stress, pressure, effort, adaptation, environment.*

Introduction

In all societies, healthcare has always been in the center of attention as a topical issue. In the context of global crises (the coronavirus pandemic of 2020-2021 can be cited as a clear example), it has once again become clear that the problem of preserving public health has both theoretical and practical relevance not only at the physiological and physical level, but also at the socio-psychological level. In the context of rapid changes in the economic, demographic, ethnic, ethical and environmental spheres of public life, there is a strong pressure on everyone. Working in a state of constant mental stress causes a decline in mental processes - memory, attention, thinking indicators, a decrease in work patterns, emotional exhaustion and, as a result, an increase in the number of occupational diseases.

Usually, the vast majority of the population understands health as a defect in the organs of the body of living organisms, the absence of diseases and the ability to fully perform their functions. The term "health" is widely used as a term that refers to medical practice from a physical point of view. However, it should be noted that currently there is no generally accepted interpretation of the concept of "health".

As a rule, it is difficult to find a direct, unambiguous answer to the question of what health is. According to experts of the World Health Organization, Health - is not only the absence of any diseases and defects, but also a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being.

Recently, the demand for the concept of "mental health" and information about mental health has increased among the population. The issue of ensuring mental health is permeating the broad masses of our society, the level of knowledge is increasing, the reason is that changes in the psyche-depression, stress, anxiety, problems-are bothering us more and more. Mental health (it can also be called mental health) is regarded as the ability of an individual to overcome difficult life situations, while maintaining the most optimal emotional background and adequacy of behavior. However, in the explanatory dictionary of psychological terms, "mental health" is defined as a relatively stable state of mind characterized by a person's adaptation, interest in life, and desire for self-realization. According to modern concepts, the state of mental health of the younger generation is explained by the living conditions in its society.

The issue of public health protection also occupies an important place in our country. A number of government resolutions and decrees adopted and adopted are vivid examples. The reason is that, as we mentioned above, the problem of mental health is becoming more urgent in

our society. Young people make up the bulk of the population of our republic. This makes it clear that ensuring mental health is also important. The reason, according to a WHO survey conducted in 2021: it found that 4 out of 10 (42%) students feel sad or hopeless, while 1/3 of students (29%) believe that they have mental health problems.

In the chapter current state and existing problems of the public education system "concepts of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 29.04.2019 No. PF-5712, it is stated that " about 25% of the total number of graduates of higher educational institutions are graduates of the specialty "Pedagogy", and this specialty should become one of the mass ones. despite this, the motivation of graduates of higher educational institutions of pedagogical profile to work in their profession due to its low attractiveness remains at a low level""

According to the Statistics agency, 86,458 students graduated from higher educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022. It follows that the number of graduates of the pedagogical direction is 28,190 people.

There are also a number of tasks that we must take into account the presence of various mental stresses, professional stresses, emotional impacts that future teaching staff may face in their teaching activities, identifying negative consequences for the mental health of future teachers, and their prevention.

Literature analysis. Since the early years of this century, several scientific studies have been conducted in the field of mental health, and the results again lead to other scientific studies. Research on mental health, physiological, social, and psychosomatic factors and causes that affect it was focused on the current level. In particular, the following studies also encourage us to focus on confirming our batch:

According to a 2003 study by Angerer, experiences acquired as a result of occupational stress and stress that occur during the course of an activity usually directly contribute to employee fatigue, burnout, which leads to a negative impact on workplace productivity and productivity, as well as job satisfaction and commitment (Angerer, 2003);

A number of studies by M.Aslach, W.Aufeli, and Leiter argue that mental health plays a key role in many areas of daily activity, including productivity and the stress level associated with it.

The scientific research of Gervving, Grayson, Alvarez, and Stoiber expresses the fact that the teaching profession is a profession associated with services related to high levels of stress and burnout.

The process of fatigue, exhaustion of pedagogical activity begins at the initial stages of the activity of pedagogical personnel, the occurrence of which is established by research. One of the main reasons given is the fact that many teachers who work in schools for a certain period of time inform future students-teachers about great stress during training, transmit information. The information obtained as a result of the above-mentioned studies makes us constantly pay attention to the task of ensuring the mental health of future teachers as one of the most pressing issues.

While studies by Fontana and Abuzeri in the early twentieth century showed that stress that occurs during the work of teachers is widespread in the teaching profession in all countries and at different stages of education, a study by researcher Harney showed that people working in the teaching profession report high levels of stress at work everywhere. (Fontana and Abouserie, Harney, 2008); The cause of teachers' stress is characterized by negative emotional experiences of

teachers, resulting from general requirements (moral, formal, spiritual) in the course of their professional activities (adaptation of curricula to meet different needs of students, or as an example, a state of frustration, depression that occurs when teachers are not able to meet their own needs) are solving behavioral problems of high school students).

Discussion and results. In order to study the factors that determine the mental health of future teachers, it is advisable to conduct a diagnosis and determine a statistical analysis of the results obtained. In the course of this study, we conducted "Questionnaire on the professional identity of future teachers" in order to identify teachers at the final stage of the level of perception of themselves as a tool for development, self-awareness in their chosen professional activity, place in a new team, awareness of their identity and assess the significance of membership in it. 118 subjects took part in our survey. Our questionnaire consists of a total of 21 questions, and the student determines their answers to the questions asked, choosing the one that best suits them, in the following form:

1	Approve / +
2	I don't approve / -

The results are analyzed using the following 4 scales. In this:

1-scale	<i>"Positive emotions associated with meeting the needs of a student in the profession"</i>
2-scale	<i>"Negative emotions associated with meeting the needs of a student in the profession"</i>
3- scale	<i>"Position of the student's active attitude to the profession"</i>
4- scale	<i>"The position of a student's passive attitude to the profession"</i>

Analysis of the survey results showed that 15.3% of future teachers (18 subjects) have a high priority for negative emotions associated with meeting the needs of the profession, and 11% have a high position of passive attitude to the profession. In conclusion, we can say that currently for students studying in the pedagogical direction, 4+2 is introduced, i.e., 4 days in a higher educational institution, 2 days in pre-school and general education schools in the order of practical training. This creates great opportunities for future teachers. Strengthen your theoretical knowledge in practice, constantly work on yourself, conduct research. At the same time, it is necessary to solve a number of tasks to prevent the occurrence of various mental stresses, professional stresses, emotional influences, negative effects on the mental health of future teachers, which may occur in teaching activities.

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